

Silhouette assessment

Veillez remplir le questionnaire ci-dessous.

Merci !

Choose the value that best reflects your current appearance.

1 14 27

Progress bar scale

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Choose the value that corresponds to the silhouette you would like to look like.

1 14 27

Progress bar scale

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Choose the value that best reflects your current appearance.

1 14 27

Progress bar scale

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Choose the value that corresponds to the silhouette you would like to look like.

1 14 27

Progress bar scale

(Place a mark on the scale above)

Silhouette actuelle

Silhouette voulue
